

Research Paper

Cochlear health alters the polarity effect and spike-initiation sites in guinea pigs

Wiebke Konerding^{a,*}, Julie Arenberg^c, Andrej Kral^{a,b,c}, Peter Baumhoff^{a,b}

^a Department of Experimental Otology, Hannover Medical School, Stadtfeldamm 34, 30625 Hannover, Germany

^b Lower Saxony Center for Biomedical Engineering, Implant Research and Development (NIFE), Germany

^c Massachusetts Eye and Ear Infirmary, Harvard Medical School, 243 Charles St, Boston, MA 02114, USA

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Polarity effect
Electrically-evoked compound action potential
Cochlear health
Cochlear implant stimulation
Spiral ganglion neuron
Guinea pig

ABSTRACT

While cochlear implants (CIs) historically use cathodic-leading pulses for stimulation, studies in humans found that anodic-leading pulses are perceived louder than cathodic-leading ones. Modeling studies proposed that cathodic pulses excite the spiral ganglion neurons (SGNs) more peripherally than anodic pulses. Thus, the anodic-benefit in human CI listeners is thought to reflect degenerated peripheral processes.

We used an animal model to test the contributions of peripheral dendrites and central axons of SGNs to polarity-effectiveness in CI stimulation. We mechanically lesioned the SGN (~400 μm diameter; $n = 18$ cochleae) and introduced a 9-day degeneration time ($n = 13$ cochleae) to mimic human SGN degeneration. These lesions were compared to 20 control ears. We stimulated via a guinea-pig adjusted CI with symmetric, biphasic pulses (monopolar mode) of alternating leading-phase polarity (50 μs /phase). Electrically-evoked compound action potential recordings to anodic- and cathodic-leading pulses were separated in the analysis to calculate the polarity effect.

We confirmed the cathodic-benefit for cochleae with healthy SGN (lower threshold, larger amplitudes, dynamic ranges, and steeper slopes). Longer latencies (50–70 μs) to cathodic than anodic monophasic and biphasic pulses confirmed the proposed peripheral (cathodic) and central (anodic) spike-initiation sites. The cathodic benefit persisted after acute lesioning, which prolonged latencies for anodic- but not for cathodic-leading pulses – consistent with remaining structures being excited by both polarities. After chronic degeneration, the threshold showed polarity-specific changes, leading to an anodic-benefit.

The observed decline in cathodic-effectiveness with reduced neural health confirmed theoretical considerations for human CI users with stimulus-polarity and degeneration-type dependent changes in spike-initiation site.

1. Introduction

Cochlear implants (CI) are neural prostheses that bypass affected sensory cells in the organ of Corti to directly, electrically stimulate the spiral ganglion neurons (SGN) that constitute the auditory nerve. Thereby, perceived loudness depends on the amount of electrical charge delivered by the electrode contacts, which is usually achieved by increasing the current level (Macherey et al., 2017). The clinically available stimulation configurations have been optimized to allow for low thresholds (i.e., low current consumption and thus, prolonged battery live) and large dynamic ranges within the safe-charge limits. Most contemporary CI manufactures accomplish this by monopolar

stimulation via an extra-cochlear return electrode. Additionally, biphasic pulses (i.e., two pulses of opposite polarity in short temporal succession) assure charge balancing, necessary for long-term biocompatibility (Loeb et al., 1983). Furthermore, most contemporary manufacturers use cathodic-leading pulses as the cathodic current has lower thresholds with more peripheral sites of activation as established in animal models (e.g., Van den Honert and Stypulkowski, 1987; for review see Carlyon and Goehring, 2021)

However, human CI listeners usually are perceptually more sensitive to anodic than to cathodic currents, especially for stimulation with supra-threshold current levels (for review see: Carlyon et al., 2013; He et al., 2017). This higher anodic efficiency has been confirmed with

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: konerding.wiebke@mh-hannover.de (W. Konerding).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2025.109341>

Received 3 January 2025; Received in revised form 17 June 2025; Accepted 19 June 2025

Available online 25 June 2025

0378-5955/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Fig. 1. – Sequence of interventions of two different experiments, performed in a total 33 guinea pigs. For comparison of acutely- and chronically lesioned ears to cochleae with healthy spiral ganglion neurons, we used a combined control group of pre-lesion measurements (top row: experiment 1) and measurements from the second, control ear of 8 chronic animals (bottom row: experiment 2). Prior to the eCAP measurements, the ears were pharmacologically deafened to prevent artefacts due to electric stimulation of hair cells.

objective measures, such as the electrically evoked compound action potential (eCAP; Bahmer and Baumann, 2013; Hughes et al., 2017; Macherey, et al., 2008; Spitzer et al., 2019; Undurraga et al., 2010; Xu et al., 2020). Specifically, larger amplitudes and steeper slopes of the eCAP amplitude growth function have been reported for anodic-leading than cathodic-leading pulses (e.g., Macherey, et al., 2008; Undurraga et al., 2010; Xu et al., 2020). As CI users often have a history of prolonged deafness, it has been proposed that this anodic-benefit reflects degeneration of peripheral processes, which would alter cathodic, but not anodic stimulation (Jahn and Arenberg, 2019a). This hypothesis is concordant with modelling data, which suggest that the central axons of SGNs have lower thresholds for anodic than cathodic currents, with the latter, preferentially eliciting spikes at peripheral processes or close to the somata (Heshmat et al., 2021; Rattay et al., 2001a, 2001b). However, these are average findings and spike-initiation sites can vary, e.g., based on pulse shape or electrode position (Kalkman et al., 2022). Evidence consistent with a neural-health rationale comes from human studies. Thereby, CI contacts that evoke lower overall thresholds or higher spectro-temporal modulation detection rates (i.e., expected to stimulate at healthy SGN population) are likely to show a cathodic-benefit with lower thresholds and higher dynamic ranges for cathodic- than anodic-dominant stimuli (Carlyon et al., 2018; Jahn and Arenberg, 2020; Mesnildrey et al., 2020; but see, Kalkman et al., 2022). Still, the suitability of the polarity effect (PE; i.e., difference between responses to cathodic vs anodic pulses) as a marker of neuronal health is highly debated (e.g., Brochier et al., 2021; Kalkman et al., 2022).

Animal models enable direct testing of the hypothesis as they allow us to determine the proposed dependency of the PE on histologically verified, cochlear health. Although animal studies often confirmed the higher efficiency of cathodic stimulation for intact SGNs over a variety of different pulse shapes and durations (e.g., Navntoft et al., 2020), we are not aware of any study that assessed potential changes in PE with histologically confirmed degeneration of the SGNs (for review see, Skidmore et al., 2022a). There is indirect evidence that the PE does not change with neural health as estimated by duration of deafness (Macherey and Cazals, 2016). To test the hypothesis, we used a mechanical micro-lesion (size in the range of CI-contact spacing) to assess whether the PE is distinctively affected when stimulating close to a region of degenerated SGN. In our previous study, we found that for ‘acute’ eCAP recordings (i.e., within hours after lesioning) the absolute PE significantly increased (i.e., lower cathodic than anodic threshold) when stimulating close to sites with damaged somata (Konerding et al., 2022). This change in PE was not observed for stimulation at a CI contact of the same electrode array 2–3 mm from the lesion (Konerding et al.,

2022). As these acute lesions have no clinical equivalent, we expanded our animal model by introducing a degeneration period after lesioning before performing the experiments. We histologically verified the degeneration of peripheral-to-central structures of the SGN resembling the clinical situation (see also, Konerding et al., 2025) as reported for different aetiologies of deafness and/or during aging (for review see, Lang, 2016).

Previously, we did not observe the expected higher cathodic efficiency for intact SGNs (Konerding et al., 2022). We attributed this lack of significant PE to the relatively low samples size. Therefore, we expanded our data base to include for each polarity 88 control measurements (instead of 17, Konerding et al., 2022), 55 acute lesions (instead of 31, Konerding et al., 2022) and recordings after chronic degeneration at the lesion ($n = 75$; differently analysed in Konerding et al., 2025). Although monophasic pulses can inform about the distinct effects of each polarity in isolation, they are not comparable to the situation in humans as they neglect the complex interaction of the two polarities when presented in close succession (e.g., Miller et al., 2001). Thus, the study was focused on the clinically relevant symmetric, charge-balanced biphasic pulses with opposite leading-phase polarities. We propose that the eCAP recordings will not only inform about differences in stimulus efficiency, but also about the spike-initiation site along the neuron. It was proposed that the CAP is generated when synchronous action potentials, propagated orthodromically along the SGN central axon, are passing the electrical barrier of the dura mater (Brown and Patuzzi, 2010; Rattay and Danner, 2014). Thus, we expect longer eCAP peak-latencies when the initiation site is peripheral, as compared to central in the range of the somatic delay ($\sim 180 \mu\text{s}$ for an action potential to be initiated at the SGN soma; Miller et al., 1999) (Miller et al., 2004; Rattay and Danner, 2014). To further test this assumption, we additionally included monophasic stimulation in control ears ($n = 18$ measurements). To be able to assess the short delays at the eCAP-level, we analyse the artefact-free late components (~ 1 ms from stimulus onset). These components, that are hypothesised to either reflect spiking of a different neural population (Dong et al., 2022) or a second spiking event of the same population (Dong et al., 2022; Ramekers et al., 2015) have similar I/O characteristics to averaged early N1P1 eCAP components (Konerding et al., 2022, 2025). To address the diverse effects on latencies (see discussion) we utilize our lesion model with SGN damage at distinct positions along the SGN (i.e., peripheral to, or at the SGN somata).

Fig. 2. – Visualization of the relative position of the CI contacts (1–6) to the lesion (red), here, indicated at the 3-D reconstructed Rosenthals' canal (yellow) as based on micro-computed tomography imaging. an: auditory nerve, CI: cochlear implant, coch: cochleostomy, ma: maleus, rc: Rosenthals' canal, rw: round window niche, osl: osseus spiral lamina.

2. Methods

2.1. Animals

The experiments were performed in 33 guinea pigs (16 female) that were either lesioned acutely ($n = 13$), chronically ($n = 13$) or not at all ($n = 7$). All experimental procedures were in accordance with German and European Union guidelines for animal welfare (ETS 123, Directive 2010/63/EU) and were approved by the German state authority (Lower Saxony state office for consumer protection and food safety, LAVES; approval No. 18/2789 and 20/3383) and monitored by the animal welfare officer of the Hannover Medical School. A subset of the experiments has been previously published with a different research question (Konerding et al., 2022).

2.2. Lesioning procedure

Lesioning was performed in a total of 31 ears: $n = 18$ acutely lesioned ears (monaural or binaural lesion in 13 animals) and $n = 13$ chronically degenerated ears (monaural lesion in 13 animals). The data was supplemented by recordings from 20 control ears that followed the same sequence of interventions (Fig. 1) as either the acute ($n = 12$ pre-lesion measurements) or the chronically lesioned ears, but without lesion ($n =$

8). Additional 5 control ears (sequence identical to pre-lesion ears, Fig. 1) were included to assess responses to monophasic stimulation. Directly prior to eCAP recordings (see 2.3), all ears were pharmacologically deafened (neomycin-sulfate infusion into scala tympani; Caesar&Lorentz GmbH, Hilden, Germany, 5 % in saline) to prevent contamination by electric stimulation of the hair cells. Hearing status was confirmed prior to deafening, via click-evoked auditory brainstem response measurements.

The process of mechanical micro-lesioning at the basal cochlear turn has been described in detail previously (Konerding et al., 2022). In short, the bulla was opened after a retro-auricular incision and a needle electrode (TECA elite needle electrode 75 mm \times 26 G, Natus Neurology, Galway, Ireland) with a sharp, tapered tip was manually inserted through a cochleostomy to puncture either Rosenthal's canal (soma lesion) or the peripheral processes (dendritic lesion). This method leads to an average SGN damage narrower than the distance of two adjacent CI contacts (contact spacing: 700 μ m).

For both the acute and the chronic lesioning, all interventions were performed under general anaesthesia. All electrophysiological recordings (2.3) were performed under isoflurane anaesthesia (<1.5 % isoflurane in O₂/air) as established in our lab (for details see Konerding et al., 2022, 2023). The acute lesions were performed within the same session, directly prior to the recordings. The chronic lesions were

Fig. 3. – Median eCAP-responses of control cochleae revealed differences between polarities, with cathodic stimulation (blue) leading to higher peak-to-peak amplitudes and longer latencies than anodic stimulation (red). The averaged responses are illustrated for stimulation at 3 dB above threshold (i.e., higher threshold of the two polarities) in monopolar configuration (reference behind the contralateral ear) via the most apical contact of a guinea-pig adjusted CI (CI#1) and recording from a ball electrode at the round window niche. Given are medians (solid line; $n = 19$) and inter-quartile ranges (areas; stimulus: 50µs/phase, no inter-phase gap). A) In the whole signal the time window affected by the artefact is highlighted (shaded area). The artefact often covered the N1 component (here: discernible only for anodic-leading stimulation) especially for cathodic-leading stimulation. B) Therefore, the analysis of the separated polarities was based on the late N2P2-components. Due to the DC-shift introduced by the artefact (see A) this shift was subtracted prior to peak-analysis (compare A and B for effect of ‘detrending’). C) The derived N2P2 was used to assess the characteristics of the input/output function via sigmoidal fitting. Sigmoidal-fitting curves showed significantly higher maximal amplitudes (Max) and dynamic ranges (dashed lines; current range from 10–90 % of Max) for cathodic- than anodic-leading stimulation.

performed under general, reversible fentanyl-midazolam-medetomidine (FMM) anaesthesia (0.2 mg/kg, 1 mg/kg, 0.025 mg/kg) under aseptic conditions (Konerding et al., 2025). Post-surgery, the anaesthesia was partly reversed (1 mg/kg atipamezole and 0.1 mg/kg flumazenil) to maintain the analgesic effect of fentanyl and the animals received further analgesic (0.2 mg/kg meloxicam) and antibiotic (10 mg/kg enrofloxacin) treatment. Following the 8–12-day (mean: 9 days) degeneration time we performed the electrophysiological recordings as detailed in 2.3.

After the recordings, the animals were sacrificed during deep anaesthesia via injection of 1000 mg pentobarbital-sodium and the cochleae were fixated in methanal solution for histological preparation. The histological preparations were described previously (for detail see Konerding et al., 2022). From 3-D reconstructions of micro-computed tomography images (Fig. 2) we confirmed CI-contact positions relative to the lesion site and via whole-mount images of the cleared cochlea, we assessed the lesion size as the maximal apical-basal extent of damaged structures (in µm).

2.3. Cochlear implant stimulation and electrically-evoked compound action potentials (eCAP)

The efficiency of the two leading-phase (biphasic) or isolated (monophasic) polarities in healthy cochleae, as well as potential changes after acute lesioning and chronic degeneration of the SGN (biphasic) was assessed via eCAP recording. The control group consisted of a combined group of the contralateral, un-lesioned cochleae of animals from the chronic group, pre-lesion measurements at acutely-lesioned cochleae and control animals (Fig. 1). The recordings were performed to stimulation on different intra-scalar CI contacts with alternating leading-phase polarity at different input-current levels to cover the dynamic range.

The details of CI stimulation were described previously (Konerding et al., 2022, 2023). In short, we used 6-contact, guinea pig-adjusted CIs (MedEl comp., Innsbruck, Austria) that were inserted through the cochleostomy into the scala tympani (Fig. 2). Electrical stimulation was performed via a custom-build electrophysiological setup (AudiologyLab, Otoconsult Comp., Frankfurt/M., Germany) with symmetric biphasic (50µs/ phase, no inter-phase-gap) or monophasic (50µs) pulses in monopolar configuration (subcutaneous Ag/AgCl electrode, behind the contralateral ear). The eCAP recording (for further details see, Konerding et al., 2022, 2023) was performed via AudiologyLab software, using

a 32-channel MIO card (NI-6259; National Instruments, Austin, USA; sampling frequency: 250 Hz). For recording we used a ball electrode ($\phi < 500$ µm; Ag/AgCl; Teflon-insulated wire) at the round window niche, referenced to an ipsilateral, retro-auricular, subcutaneous Ag/AgCl wire.

2.4. Polarity-specific input-output function of late eCAP components

The analysis of the late eCAP components (N2P2) has been described previously (Konerding et al., 2022). In short, we assessed the N2P2 peak-to-peak amplitudes in an artefact-free time-window (N2: 0.7–1.2 ms; P2: 1.1–1.6 ms) to separately analyse the eCAP input/output (I/O) functions (also called amplitude-growth functions) in response to the two leading-phase polarities. The data was averaged for each polarity separately (150 sweeps) to derive the eCAP trace at each input-intensity and pre-processed using Matlab routines (3rd order sgolay filter with 63-sample frame length; detrending). To describe the characteristics of the I/O functions, we used sigmoidal fitting (Matlab non-linear least squares fit) as previously used in the field (e.g., Ramekers et al., 2014).

$$V(I) = A + \frac{B}{1 + e^{-\frac{I-C}{D}}} \quad (1)$$

where V is amplitude in microvolts (µV), I is stimulus current level in decibel (dB attenuation; dB_{att}), and A – D are the fitted eCAP parameters: A) lower asymptote, B) upper asymptote (from here: maximal amplitude), and D) the current-level at the inflection point (EC50). Due to base-line correction (i.e., subtraction of the average subthreshold amplitudes), the lower asymptote was always fitted as 0µV. Of these I/O characteristics, we derived the following parameters: threshold as stimulation current leading to 10 % of the fitted maximum, dynamic range (DR) as dB-difference from threshold-level to 90 % of the maximum, and slope as $B/4D$ in mV/dB (e.g., Ramekers et al., 2014; Skidmore et al., 2022b). The threshold current level was recalculated into current in µA (10 mV ~ 0dBatt; for details see Konerding et al., 2025). We excluded measurements with low goodness of fit ($r^2 < 0.8$; 23 out of 474 I/O functions).

2.5. Polarity effect (PE)

The PE was calculated as the normalized cathodic-anodic difference (re mean in percentage) for each of the four different I/O characteristics (threshold, maximal amplitude, dynamic range, and slope) as

Fig. 4. – Difference in eCAP characteristic between anodic-leading (red) and cathodic-leading (aqua) pulses for stimulation at all 6 CI contacts, separately (symmetric, biphasic pulses, monopolar mode) in 20 control cochleae. The sample size was similar between contacts ($N = 88$ per polarity; #1: $n = 19$, #2: $n = 12$, #3: $n = 12$, #4: $n = 11$, #5: $n = 17$, #6: $n = 17$) with some missing values for latency at 1 dB ($N = 75$ per polarity; min: $n = 10$) and 8 dB above threshold ($N = 63$ per polarity; min: $n = 9$). Depicted are means (symbol) and standard errors of the mean (whisker). A-D) In addition to the original values, the derived polarity-effect (PE) is indicated as inset (bottom, right Y-axis) calculated as relative difference of the two polarities (re mean). The blue box highlights PE-ranges in the direction of a cathodic-benefit. E&F) For the latency at 1 and 8 dB above threshold, the PE was calculated as absolute difference in ms. 2-way ANOVA with post-test statistics (Bonferroni corrected) for pairwise comparison of polarities indicated above the graphs: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

$$PE = \frac{cathodic - anodic}{(cathodic + anodic)/2} * 100 \text{ [%]} \quad (2)$$

Whereby, the N2-latency PE (at 1 and 8 dB above threshold) was given as the absolute cathodic-anodic difference in ms. For both calculations, negative PE values indicate a higher value for anodic-leading stimulation as compared to cathodic-leading stimulation and positive values indicate a higher value for cathodic-leading stimulation as compared to anodic-leading stimulation. A maximum of 218 PE-calculations were included in the analysis of each eCAP characteristic (control: $n = 88$, acute: $n = 55$, chronic: $n = 75$), with reduced sample sizes for latencies as indicated in the results.

2.6. Statistical analysis

We performed group analyses with leading-phase polarities as dependent variable and CI-contact (not all available for each ear), or lesion group ($n = 3$) as independent variable. To analyse the effect of stimulating close to lesion, we used stimulation at the most apical (#1) contact as ‘OFF’ lesion stimulation and stimulation at the most basal (#6) contact as the ‘ON’ lesion stimulation (Konerding et al., 2022). The lesion-position information (ON vs. OFF) was included as dependent variable in the group analysis, leading to reduced sample sizes in some cases, as detailed in the results section. When the group analysis (ANOVA) yielded significant group differences, these were further specified using post-tests controlled for multiple comparisons. To assess the dependency of the PE to the histologically derived lesion size we

Table 1

- Statistical comparisons of the two polarities (paired) at all 6 CI contacts (unpaired) for different eCAP characteristics. The latency of the N2 component is given both for stimulation at 1 dB and at 8 dB above threshold. Given are results of the 2-way ANOVA (polarity: $df=1$, CI contact: $df=5$, interaction term: $df=5$) with post-test on the polarity effect at each stimulation contact (CI#1–6). Significant results are indicated in bold-green.

		ANOVA			Bonferroni corrected post-test per CI #					
		residuals	F	p	1	2	3	4	5	6
threshold [μ A]	Polarity	82	9.375	0.0030	*					
	CI contact		5.872	0.0001						
	Interaction		1.154	0.3389						
Max [mV]	Polarity	82	305.3	<0.0001	***	***	***	***	***	***
	CI contact		0.274	0.9264						
	Interaction		0.2675	0.9296						
dynamic [dB]	Polarity	82	50.34	<0.0001	**	*			*	***
	CI contact		0.1773	0.9704						
	Interaction		0.5621	0.7287						
slope [mV/dB]	Polarity	82	164.0	<0.0001				*		
	CI contact		0.3785	0.8621						
	Interaction		0.3257	0.8961						
Latency 1 dB [ms]	Polarity	69	42.40	<0.0001	***	**				
	CI contact		1.247	0.2968						
	Interaction		1.062	0.3892						
Latency 8 dB [ms]	Polarity	57	89.87	<0.0001		**	**	***	***	***
	CI contact		0.1570	0.9770						
	Interaction		1.026	0.4113						

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

used Spearman correlations. The analyses were performed via GraphPadPrism (Version 5.02, GraphPad Software Inc., Boston, USA) with a level of significance set to 5 %. Prior to testing, we assessed normal distributions with Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests (with Dallal-Wilkinson-Lilliefor p value) and performed non-parametric tests, if normality was not confirmed.

3. Results

All averaged eCAP traces contained both the early N1P1 component and the later N2P2 component (Fig. 3A). For artefact-free analysis of the alternating leading-phase polarities we chose the late N2P2 components (Fig. 3B; for details see Konerding et al., 2022). The N2P2 analysis enabled reliable sigmoidal fitting (Fig. 3C) in most cases, which was defined as a goodness of fit exceeding 0.8 (average $r^2=0.98$; in $n = 232$ cathodic and $n = 219$ anodic I/O functions).

3.1. The polarity effect when stimulating intact spiral ganglion neurons

Based on visual inspection of the eCAP traces in control ears (stimulation at the most apical contact #1; Fig. 2) the N2-P2 amplitude (Fig. 3B) was higher for cathodic-leading than anodic-leading pulses. This difference between stimulation polarities further increased with increasing stimulation current (Fig. 3C) due to the larger dynamic range and steeper slope in response to cathodic-, as compared to anodic-leading pulses (see also Fig. 4).

Group analyses confirmed the above observations: There was a significant difference between anodic and cathodic I/O characteristics in control measurements (2-way ANOVA; post-test with pairwise-comparison of polarity; Table 1, Fig. 4). Cathodic-leading pulses, as compared to anodic-leading pulses, required less current to reach threshold (Fig. 4A) led to higher amplitudes (Fig. 4B) larger dynamic ranges (Fig. 4C) and steeper slopes (Fig. 4D). Furthermore, the N2 latency was longer for cathodic- than anodic leading pulses (Fig. 4E&F).

Fig. 5. – The efficacy of the two leading-phase polarities changed throughout the dynamic range: from threshold (10 % maximal amplitude) over inflection point (EC50) to maximal amplitude (max). Whereas the cathodic-leading pulse needed $\sim 1/2$ dB less current than the anodic-leading pulse to reach threshold (i.e., 10 % of maximal amplitude) it needed ~ 3 dB more current to evoke its respective (i.e., higher) maximal amplitude. Given are boxplots for averaged values over all 6 CI contacts (mean; $N = 20$). Friedman test ($p < 0.0001$) with Dunn's multiple comparison test (top): * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$. Wilcoxon test and t -test vs. null-distribution (bottom): * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Table 2

– Statistical comparisons of the PE (mean over all CI contacts) for different eCAP characteristics for the 3 lesion groups: control, acute lesion and chronic degeneration. Given are the *t*-test or Wilcoxon test (*W*; non-parametric) vs. null-distribution to indicate significant differences between polarities for each group as well as 1-way ANOVA or Kruskal-Wallis tests (*K*; non-parametric) for group comparisons of PEs with post-test against controls. Significant differences to zero are indicated in bold-green. None of the group comparisons reached significance ($p > 0.05$).

Polarity effect		N=	Median	Test vs. 0		Group comparison	
				statistic	p-value	statistic	p-value
Threshold [%]	Control	20	−6.656	W=−110.0	0.0419	<i>K</i> = 2.827	0.2433
	Acute	18	−4.226	<i>W</i> =−53.0	0.2575		
	Chronic	13	1.889	<i>t</i> = 0.7862	0.4470		
Max [%]	Control	20	67.77	<i>t</i> = 9.272	<0.0001	<i>F</i> = 0.802	0.4542
	Acute	18	63.22	<i>t</i> = 9.941	<0.0001		
	Chronic	13	55.83	<i>t</i> = 11.93	<0.0001		
Dynamic [%]	Control	20	39.42	<i>t</i> = 4.196	0.0005	<i>F</i> = 1.756	0.1836
	Acute	18	17.64	<i>t</i> = 2.334	0.0321		
	Chronic	13	27.77	<i>t</i> = 2.038	0.0642		
Slope [%]	Control	20	96.23	<i>t</i> = 3.759	0.0013	<i>K</i> = 2.779	0.2492
	Acute	18	84.04	W = 171.0	0.0002		
	Chronic	13	78.82	<i>t</i> = 2.154	0.0523		
latency _{1dB} [μs]	Control	20	80.0	<i>W</i> = 85.0	0.9070	<i>K</i> = 3.264	0.1955
	Acute	18	−77.5	<i>t</i> = 0.974	0.3437		
	Chronic	13	114.0	<i>t</i> = 3.234	0.0072		
latency _{8dB} [μs]	Control	12	40.0	<i>t</i> = 10.940	<0.0001	<i>K</i> = 3.888	0.1431
	Acute	6	44.0	<i>t</i> = 7.986	0.0005		
	Chronic	3	26.0	<i>W</i> = 6.0	0.2500		

The effects were present for stimulation throughout all 6 CI contacts (i. e., no significant interaction between CI contact and polarity). The longer latencies for cathodic (mean+SD 0.838+0.093 ms, $n = 14$) than anodic stimulation (0.791+0.058 ms) were confirmed with monophasic stimulation at 8 dB above threshold (2-way ANOVA Polarity: $F(1,8)=10.07$, $p = 0.0131$, CI contact: $F(5,8)=0.5244$, $p = 0.7527$, Interaction: $F(5,8)=2.351$, $p = 0.1353$) and are consistent with our assumptions that the cathodic phase excites the peripheral processes and that the eCAPs obtained here measure the response of the central axons. The monophasic threshold showed the known apical-basal gradient and was also affected by polarity, however, with reversed sign, as compared to biphasic stimulation (anodic: 244.1 + 48,14 μA, cathodic 276.3 + 70.71 μA; Polarity: $F(1,8)=6.208$, $p = 0.0284$, CI contact: $F(5,8)=7.208$, $p = 0.0025$, Interaction: $F(5,8)=0.7116$, $p = 0.6264$). Other aspects of the monophasic I/O function were not significantly affected by polarity (Polarity: $F(1,8) \leq 1.502$, $p \geq 0.2439$, CI contact: $F(5,8) \leq 0.8354$, $p \geq 0.5492$, Interaction: $F(5,8) \leq 0.6179$, $p \geq 0.6890$), that is slope (0.176+0.324 mV/dB), dynamic range (5.530+2.880 dB), and maximal amplitude (0.498+0.743 mV).

3.2. Polarity dependent efficacy along the I/O function

Whereas the eCAP amplitude (i.e., efficiency) was consistently larger for cathodic- than anodic-leading pulses already at 1 dB above threshold (mean+SD: cathodic: 54.0 + 20.9 μV, anodic: 41.5 + 16.6 μV; 2-way ANOVA Polarity: $F(1,69)=32.76$, $p < 0.0001$, CI contact: $F(5,69)=0.887$, $p = 0.4948$, Interaction: $F(5,69)=2.337$, $p = 0.0509$) the polarity effect on the current needed to reach a respective point along the dynamic (i.e., efficacy) changed from a cathodic- to an anodic benefit along the I/O function. The stimulation with cathodic-leading pulses reached threshold (i.e., current needed to reach 10 % of maximal amplitude; Fig. 4) at significantly lower current levels than the one with anodic-leading pulses (Wilcoxon test vs null-distribution: $W=-110$, $p = 0.0419$). However, due to the described PE for the dynamic range (DR PE), the polarity dependent efficacy changed for supra-threshold amplitudes: The current needed to reach the polarity-specific maximal amplitude (see Fig. 5) was significantly higher for cathodic than anodic pulses (*t*-test vs null-distribution: $t = 4.319$, $p = 0.0004$). For direct comparison with human literature (see discussion), the PE was (re) calculated as difference in dB (Fig. 5), with negative values indicating that less current was needed for cathodic- than anodic-leading pulses to reach equal points along the dynamic range. The change from negative

to positive PE from threshold, over the inflection point (EC50) to maximal current, was significant at the group level (Friedman test: $F = 25.60$, $p < 0.0001$) with significant differences between all 3 points along the dynamic (Dunn's post-test for correction of multiple testing: $p < 0.05$; Fig. 5).

3.3. The effect of SGN lesions and degeneration on the polarity effect

To assess differences between study groups, we averaged the PE across all stimulated CI contacts (mean) for each individual cochlea (for contact-specific analysis see 3.4 and 3.5). There was no significant difference based on the lesion type (Table 2), with overall similar median PE for all 3 groups (Fig. 6). To consider the apical-basal gradient observed for the eCAP threshold, we repeated this analysis for stimulation at the most basal contact (CI#6; i.e., close to the lesion-site) which yielded a similar result (Kruskal-Wallis tests: $K = 2.252$, $p = 0.1078$).

3.4. The PE effect for soma lesions

In our previous study (Konerding et al., 2022), the acute micro-lesions affected the threshold PE for soma lesions, but not for lesions restricted to peripheral dendrites (i.e., relative to pre-lesion measurements). Thus, we compared the PE for 'ON' and 'OFF' lesion for soma lesions (acute damage and chronic degeneration). Therefore, the lesions were categorised as either dendrite lesions (i.e., only peripheral processes were affected) or soma lesions (i.e., with additional loss of SGN nuclei), using histological images of the cleared cochlea (Fig. 7). Before restricting the analysis to the soma lesions, we confirmed that the lesions were similar in size, irrespective of the lesion target. Furthermore, the lesion size was derived as apical-basal extent of the lesion (i.e., dark areas indicating cell loss; Fig. 7).

As expected, there was a noticeable larger lesion size for chronic than acute lesions, indicating the degenerative process that damaged SGN structures beyond the initial (acute) lesion (Fig. 8). However, the lesion sizes were comparable between histologically identified dendritic (acute: $n = 5$, chronic: $n = 4$) and soma lesions (acute: $n = 12$, chronic: $n = 8$; 2-way ANOVA: acute-chronic: $F(1,25)=10.02$, $p = 0.004$; dendrite-soma: $F(1,25)=0.2469$, $p = 0.6236$; interaction: $F(1,25)=0.03202$, $p = 0.8594$; Fig. 8). Thus, any difference between the full-data and the soma lesion-only analysis would not be biased by the apical-basal extent of the lesion.

We used stimulation at the most apical (#1) contact as 'OFF' lesion

Fig. 6. – Similarity in polarity effect (PE) of different eCAP parameters between the controls and 2 lesion groups. Positive values indicate a higher value for stimulation with cathodic- than anodic-leading pulses. For cochleae with healthy spiral ganglion neurons ($N = 20$ controls) stimulation with the cathodic-leading polarity was more efficient than anodic-leading stimulation: A) negative PE for threshold and B-D) positive PE for amplitude, dynamic range and slope. E,F) The positive PE for latency indicates longer latencies for cathodic- than anodic-leading stimulation. After lesioning (acute: $N = 18$, chronic: $N = 13$), the median PE usually kept the same sign as in controls. A-F) There was no difference to controls for neither the acute lesion nor the chronic degeneration in any of the eCAP parameters (Table 2). Given are box-plots overlain by individual data points. T-test or Wilcoxon test vs. null-distribution (above): * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

stimulation and stimulation at the most basal (#6) contact as the ‘ON’ lesion stimulation. Due to the reduced sample size for paired comparisons of anodic- and cathodic-leading latency at 8 dB above threshold (i. e., stimulation at high current levels not measured or distorted by facial nerve responses), this parameter could not be included in the analysis. Of the PEs tested, only the threshold PE showed a significant effect of the lesion group, with significant change for stimulating ON, but not OFF lesion (Fig. 9A and 9D; repeated measure 2-way ANOVA: Table 3): Close to a chronic soma degeneration, the threshold PE changed sign (to positive PE), indicating a shift from a cathodic- to an anodic-benefit at threshold level.

3.5. Polarity dependent eCAP changes for stimulating close to soma lesions

For the threshold, which showed significant differences between lesion groups (control re chronic), we additionally compared the anodic- and cathodic-leading results for ON-lesion stimulation to assess whether the observed changes in PE were driven by one and/or the other polarity. We found a significant interaction of polarity and group (i.e., acute and chronic; 2-way ANOVA: $F(1,23)=8.303$, $p = 0.0084$): After chronic degeneration (i.e., somata and central axon) the threshold was significantly elevated for cathodic-leading pulses, but did not change significantly for anodic-leading pulses (Fig. 10A and Table 4).

Fig. 7. – Exemplary histological images of A&B) a chronic degeneration affecting the spiral ganglion (sgn) somata as compared to C) a control cochlea. A-C) The tissue is auto-fluorescent (green) due to fixation of the tissue, prior to decalcification. A) The overview shows that adjacent to the lesion (circle) with lost SGN somata in the middle (dark area) and compressed nuclei to the sides (bright area) we saw both loss of the peripheral processes (pp) and degeneration of the central axons (ca: reduced density leads to darker areas). an: auditory nerve, lw: lateral wall, oc: organ of Corti, rw: round window, sl: spiral lamina, st: scala tympani. B&C) The small stacks of the basal cochlear turn are focused on the lesion area to highlight the difference in SGN survival and organisation between B) a lesioned and C) a control cochlea. Scalebar: 500 μm.

Fig. 8. – Similarities between lesions at peripheral dendrites (triangle) and somata (circle) for both acute (orange) and chronic lesions (violet). The lesion size was on average 0.3 mm for acute lesions and 0.5 mm after chronic degeneration. Individual cochleae are indicated as symbols with mean (line) and standard deviation (whiskers) per group. All acute lesions and most chronic lesions are smaller than the spacing between two adjacent CI-contacts (dashed line).

We further included the latency at 1 dB above threshold in the analysis as these results were helpful to derive hypotheses on the spike-initiation site (see discussion). There was an overall effect of polarity (Polarity: $F(1,23)=6.723$, $p = 0.0166$, Group: $F(1,23)=1.733$, $p = 0.2001$, Interaction: $F(1,23)=0.3237$, $p = 0.7269$) with the following changes after acute soma lesioning: The N2 latency was significantly prolonged for anodic-leading pulses (mean: 1.05 ms) as compared to

anodic-controls (0.94 ms), reaching values of cathodic-stimulation (control: 1.02 ms; acute lesion: 1.08 ms; Fig. 10B, Table 4), consistent with a change in the site of excitation to a more peripheral part of the neuron. Furthermore, the average latency for cathodic-leading pulses (0.96 ms) was similar to anodic-controls. The statistical comparison to the cathodic-controls was, however, not significant (Table 4).

To assess, whether the threshold PE would also qualify as marker of

Fig. 9. - Comparison of the acute ($N = 12$) and the chronic lesion data ($N = 8$) to the control group ($N = 20$), for soma lesions, only. Given are means (symbols) with standard deviations (whiskers). A) There was a significant polarity effect for stimulating ‘ON’ lesion (i.e., most basal contact), for the eCAP threshold, with chronic soma lesions leading to elevated thresholds for cathodic-leading, as compared to anodic-leading pulses. B-E) No additional eCAP parameter showed any differences between group (DR: dynamic range). $**p < 0.01$.

neural health, we correlated it with the apical-basal extent of the soma degeneration for ON-lesion stimulation. This did, however, not reach statistical significance ($n = 10$; Pearson correlation: $p = 0.1564$, $r = 0.484$).

4. Discussion

We assessed differences in stimulation efficiency between anodic and cathodic-leading, symmetric biphasic pulses. We found a significant cathodic-benefit over a variety of tested eCAP parameters when stimulating healthy cochleae. When introducing spatially restricted lesions to the basal turn, there was only little overall change in PE. However, there was a polarity-specific effect (PE), depending on the type of lesion: Acute loss of somata led to a shift in latency PE, indicative of a change in spike initiation site and chronic soma degeneration led to a polarity-specific change in threshold, inducing an anodic-benefit for stimulating at

threshold level. In the following, we will discuss how these results support and extend the existing hypotheses on polarity-sensitivity of CI stimulation.

4.1. Efficiency of stimulating healthy SGN with biphasic pulses of opposite leading-phase polarity

For the guinea pig, there were ambiguous findings on whether the cathodic (e.g., Klop et al., 2004; Macherey and Cazals, 2016) or the anodic phase (Miller et al., 1998) is more efficient for CI stimulation. We suggest that part of the controversy is due to the pulse shape used for stimulation. Whereas we found that stimulation with biphasic cathodic-leading pulses was more efficient than stimulation with anodic-leading pulses (symmetric, $50\mu\text{s}/\text{phase}$, no IPG, in monopolar configuration) we found that monophasic anodic pulses ($50\mu\text{s}$) had lower thresholds than cathodic pulses. The latter finding was consistent

Table 3

– Statistical comparisons of the PE for different eCAP characteristics after soma lesion, comparing 3 lesion groups (independent variable: control, acute, and chronic) and 2 stimulation positions, relative to the lesion (dependent variable: ON and OFF lesion). Given are repeated measure 2-way ANOVA for group comparisons with Bonferroni corrected post-test against controls for significant group or interaction effects. Significant results are indicated in bold-green.

Polarity Effect (PE)	ANOVA			post-test vs. control	
	N pairs	F	p	ON	OFF
threshold	Group	30	6.989	0.0032	acute $p > 0.05$ chronic $p < 0.01$
	ON—OFF Interaction		3.215	0.0831	
max	Group	30	0.077	0.9262	
	ON—OFF Interaction		1.746	0.1918	
dynamic	Group	30	2.752	0.0799	
	ON—OFF Interaction		0.0018	0.9657	
slope	Group	30	2.384	0.1094	
	ON—OFF Interaction		0.968	0.3914	
Latency 1dB	Group	28	3.016	0.0651	
	ON—OFF Interaction		0.638	0.4307	

with polarity-specific threshold differences reported for pseudo-monophasic stimuli using inferior colliculus (IC) recording (Konerding et al., 2021). When presenting the two polarities in close succession, hyperpolarization blocks of one phase may partially overlap in space and time with the depolarization evoked by the other phase. This would explain higher biphasic than monophasic thresholds (e.g., Miller et al., 2001). If this effect was lower for one polarity than the other, this could explain PE reversal in our data from monophasic to biphasic stimulation. A potential explanation is the described facilitation effect of the anodic-second phase, which relieves the hyperpolarization blocks by the preceding cathodic phase (Zheng et al., 2022). In order to draw conclusions on the exact mechanism of the proposed interaction of the two phases within the biphasic pulse, it is, therefore, necessary to additionally consider the anatomical relation of the spike initiation sites. This is, however, beyond the scope of the study and the respective IC recordings are currently under investigation.

The cathodic-benefit for biphasic pulses was evident in all control animals ($N = 20$) throughout all CI contacts (i.e., located within lower to upper basal turn) as lower thresholds, larger amplitudes (from 1 dB above threshold to maximal amplitudes), larger dynamic ranges and steeper slopes. Whereas the average size of the PE was low at threshold

levels (5 % of the total mean for threshold and 1 % for latency) it increased substantially with increasing stimulus level (from 38 % for dynamic range to 70 % for maximal amplitude).

As discussed in the literature, these findings in animal models are different from the commonly observed benefit of anodic-leading biphasic pulses in human CI users which has been discussed to originate from differences in survival of peripheral processes, but also anatomy, etiology of deafness and/or differences in methodology have to be considered (for review see, Kalkman et al., 2022). Thus, we will discuss our results with a focus on general validity versus species-specificity of our findings.

4.2. Methodological considerations: changes in polarity-dependent efficacy throughout the dynamic range

Whereas we found consistent cathodic benefits throughout the whole dynamic range (e.g., higher amplitude at both 1 dB above threshold and at maximum), the anodic-benefit in humans is often reported to be present at supra-threshold levels and only inconsistently at/ close to threshold (Macherey et al., 2017). When assessing the PE, two perspectives can be taken: efficiency and efficacy. Efficiency assesses the relation of input current to output measures (e.g., eCAP amplitude) and efficacy evaluates how much current is needed to reach a desired output (e.g., loudness percept). Although there are individual differences across the array (Bierer et al., 2015) the average PE efficacy sometimes changes sign throughout the dynamic range: For human CI users the current to reach threshold has been reported to be on average 1.2 dB lower for cathodic than anodic stimuli (i.e., cathodic-benefit) whereas the current-level to reach the most-comfortable level (MCL) was 2.5 dB lower for anodic than cathodic stimulation (i.e., anodic-benefit, Guérit et al., 2020). However, these PE reversals were not observed in all CI users (Macherey et al., 2017) and depended on the interaction of amplitude and dynamic in response to the two polarities (Jahn and

Table 4

– Statistical analysis of potential changes relative to controls for chronic degeneration (threshold) and acute lesions (latency) for the two leading-phase polarities, separately. Given are test-statistics of the unpaired comparisons (t -test or Mann-Whitney U test). Significant differences to the respective control-group are indicated in bold-green.

		t-statistic	Lesion vs. Control	
			df	p-value
threshold	Anodic	0.1692	24	0.8671
	Cathodic	2.084	26	0.0471
latency 1 dB	Anodic	2.665	22	0.0141
	Cathodic	1.524	21	0.1425

Fig. 10. – Lesion-type and polarity-specific changes in eCAP parameters. A) Chronic soma degeneration led to an elevated threshold for cathodic-leading stimulation, only. B) Acute damage at the somata prolonged latencies for anodic-leading stimulation, only. Unpaired t -test: * $p < 0.05$.

Arenberg, 2019b). We could replicate this PE transition from a cathodic- to an anodic-benefit throughout the dynamic range: Whereas the current to reach threshold was 0.6 dB lower for cathodic- than anodic leading pulses, the current to reach similar supra-threshold points along the dynamic (i.e., mid-point and maximum) was lower for anodic- than cathodic leading pulses (0.7 and 2.9 dB to reach EC50 and maximal amplitude, respectively). Note, however, that the supra-threshold response at a given point on the dynamic range was larger for cathodic-leading than for anodic-leading stimuli. This effect is based on differences in the dynamic range of the two polarities (Fig. 3D) which is not present for monophasic stimuli. We therefore postulate that the shift in PE efficacy is based on the interaction of the two polarities within the biphasic pulse which changes from more local phenomena, such as hyperpolarization blocks (at threshold, see 4.1) to more global, recruitment effects (at later stages of the dynamic). This interaction is considered to be suppressive not only at threshold (see 4.1) but also at supra-threshold levels, as the maximum activation reached with either anodic or cathodic monophasic pulses are overall higher than the one for biphasic pulses of either leading-phase polarity (own data and Miller et al., 1998). Whereas this polarity specific dependency on input level (relative to the dynamic range) indicates a species-general pattern in PE efficacy, it does not explain the species-specific sign of PE in terms of eCAP amplitude (see next section).

4.3. Spike-initiation site

For control ears we found consistent supra-threshold latency PE, with 46 μ s (SD: 15 μ s) longer latencies for cathodic-leading than anodic-leading pulses. These findings were consistent in sign with monophasic stimulation reported here for eCAP data (mean PE: 47 μ s) and previously reported PE in first-spike latency for pseudo-monophasic pulses, recorded in the IC (Konerding et al., 2021). The range of latency PE at both 1 dB (PE: \sim 70 μ s) and 8 dB (PE: \sim 50 μ s) above threshold. These longer latencies to cathodic than anodic-leading pulses are consistent with findings from brainstem recordings in humans that reported shorter anodic than cathodic latencies for all tested stimulus types (i.e., biphasic and pseudo-monophasic; Undurraga et al., 2013). However, only the latency difference to pseudo-monophasic stimuli was discussed to reflect more central spike-initiation by anodic than cathodic stimulation, whereas the latency PE to symmetric biphasic pulses was in the range of the phase duration, indicating that the anodic phase was responsible for most of the excitation (Undurraga et al., 2010, 2013).

However, the broad activation due to the monopolar grounding configuration was not ideal for drawing conclusions on spike-initiation sites, especially, at supra-threshold levels. Thus, we also considered alternative explanations for our observations. First, the latency PE may have been due to the fact that the cathodic-second phase in an anodic-leading pulse was already 2–3 dB above its respective threshold, when the latencies at 1 dB above (anodic) threshold were measured. We therefore repeated the analysis on a subset of our data, comparing latencies for cathodic-leading pulses at 3 dB above threshold with those for anodic-leading pulses at 1 dB above threshold: The result was similar to the initial analysis (Wilcoxon test vs 0: $p < 0.0001$, median latency PE: 0.068 ms, $n = 123$). Thus, we conclude that the cathodic second-phase was not driving the shift towards shorter latencies in the anodic-leading pulses. Second, the activating phase may have always been the anodic one (i.e., the more efficient polarity in monophasic stimuli), which would be the initial phase in an anodic-leading pulse and the second one in a cathodic-leading pulse, leading to a 50 μ s delay of the eCAP response for cathodic-leading pulses. Although we cannot rule out this possibility, we consider it unlikely, given that the shift from a purely anodic stimulus (monophasic) to a cathodic one resulted in an identical delay (see above). Third, the recorded latency-differences may have been a side-effect of changes in amplitude, which are dependent on synchrony (high synchrony \sim high amplitude \sim short latency). However, we observed higher amplitudes, together with longer latencies for

cathodic- than for anodic-leading pulses, which goes contrary to this assumption.

Thus, we conclude that the latency PE observed here, in guinea pigs, is influenced mostly by changes in spike-initiation site. Based on recordings in cats, it was proposed that both polarities may stimulate, at distinct activation sites along the SGN, that is peripheral or central to the soma (Miller et al., 1999). Thereby, the observed bimodal latency distributions (single-cell recordings) were expected to result from somatic delay (\sim 180 μ s; Miller et al., 1999). This somatic delay is similar to the one derived by Briarie and Frijns (2005; i.e., 150 μ s) from a computer model of the human cochlea which indicates a species-general underlying mechanism. The latency difference observed in our eCAP data is smaller (40–70 μ s) but corresponds to the 40–90 μ s latency difference in cat midbrain recordings interpreted as somatic delay (Javel and Shepherd, 2000). Due to the fact that the CAP likely reflects synchronous activation at the central axon (see introduction), it is not possible to directly infer on different activation sites along the SGNs. Thus, to confirm the assumption that longer latencies are indicative of more peripheral sites of activation, we utilized the results of the lesion experiments (see 4.6).

4.4. Anatomical considerations for species-specific PEs

Whereas in humans the amplitudes to anodic-leading stimulation are usually reported to be larger than the cathodic ones and to increase more steeply with increasing stimulus level (e.g., He et al., 2017; Hughes, 2023), the opposite was evident in our data, consistent with other animal studies (for review see, Skidmore et al., 2022a). These findings are robust over a variety of pulse shapes and recording schemes (for review see, Skidmore et al., 2022a). We propose that this discrepancy in average PEs is related to cochlear anatomy. Due to significant correlations of the PE with averaged thresholds (e.g., Carlyon et al., 2018), it was initially suggested that one potential influencing factor is the distance to the excitable tissue. However, analyses in humans did not find any systematic change in PE with electrode position (insertion angle; De Groote et al., 2024) or the electrode-to-modiolus distance (threshold PE; Jahn and Arenberg, 2019a) and also our data did not lend support to the hypothesis (i.e., no significant difference between apical and basal contacts) and the electrode-to-modiolus distance was in a similar range to those reported in humans (from 0.18 to 2.2 mm; Jahn and Arenberg, 2019a) with 0.9 to 1.9 mm for CI#1 and #6, respectively ($n = 15$ ears). A recent modelling study proposes the fibre-electrode spatial relationship as relevant factor for stimulation efficiency (Fellner et al., 2024). This would lead to species differences, especially at the basal cochlear turn: Compared to guinea pigs, humans have a relatively wide basal turn with a wide curvature (Keppeler et al., 2021; Pietsch et al., 2017) leading to considerably longer peripheral processes (Iyer et al., 2016; Potrusil et al., 2020). However, the individual PE patterns for human CI patients are often erratic (Goehring et al., 2019; Jahn and Arenberg, 2019a) and it has been reported that at threshold level only about 78 % of the electrodes show the anodic benefit (Mesnildrey et al., 2020). This is likely due to the additional influence of neural health (see next section).

4.5. Changes in polarity effect (PE) with reduced neural health

The higher anodic- than cathodic efficiency in humans has been discussed to originate from reduced neural health, with degeneration of the peripheral processes leading to the observed lower thresholds/higher amplitudes for anodic stimulation (e.g., Jahn and Arenberg, 2019a, 2019b). However, this notion of the PE as marker of neural health is under debate, as the PE has not been found to correlate with estimators of neural health (age; duration of deafness) or speech perception levels (Arslan and Luo, 2022; Brochier et al., 2021; Hughes, 2022). In line with the neural-health hypothesis, we found significant differences to the controls when SGN somata were affected (i.e., indicating a complete loss of peripheral processes): There was a

Fig. 11. – Summary of hypothesised spike-initiation sites and stimulation efficiency for biphasic pulses with opposite leading-phase polarity. The spike-initiation site is indicated by the position of the letter (A: anodic-leading, C: cathodic-leading). In bold is the respective polarity with the higher efficiency for each of the 3 lesion profiles (left-to-right: no SGN lesion, acute soma damage, chronic degeneration of the somata and central structures). an: auditory nerve.

polarity-specific elevation of the threshold, resulting in reversed sign of the PE as compared to controls. This was not the case, when cochleae with restricted damaged to the peripheral processes (i.e., dendritic lesion type) were included. Computational models have shown that partially demyelinated SGN models behave similarly to healthy ones with regard to the PE, with higher thresholds for anodic/ anodic-first stimulations than for cathodic/ cathodic-first stimulations (i.e., cathodic-benefit; for review see [Recugnat, 2022](#)). Thereby, only the retraction of peripheral process caused the central shift of spike-initiation sites which are more sensitive to anodic polarities, leading to the human-typical anodic-benefit. The fact that the threshold-PE change observed in our data was mainly due to an elevation of cathodic (not anodic) thresholds further corresponds to the loss of peripheral processes. Correspondingly, human modelling studies reported that changes in threshold PE due to neural degeneration were mostly the result of changes in response to cathodic currents ([Kalkman et al., 2022](#)). These observations indicate a species-general effect of neural health on the polarity sensitivity. However, the change from a cathodic- to an anodic-benefit was limited to the threshold (e.g., no change in max PE), thereby limiting the value of the PE as marker of neural health (e.g., [Brochier et al., 2021](#); [Kalkman et al., 2022](#)). Further investigations are needed to assess additional factors on polarity-specific excitation patterns throughout the dynamic range. These may include differences in current flow, as for example due to bone porosity ([Sriperumbudur et al., 2024](#)) and the orientation of the excitable tissue within the resulting electric field ([Fellner et al., 2024](#)).

4.6. Conclusions: changes in spike-initiation site with changes in neural health

Considering the observed changes in PE after acute and chronic soma lesioning, we drew the following conclusions on spike-initiation site for symmetric biphasic pulses of opposite leading-phase polarity ([Fig. 11](#)):

1) Peripheral activation with cathodic-leading pulses

Only a chronic degeneration of the somata resulted in a threshold increase for cathodic-leading pulses, indicating the loss of the initial spike-initiation site (i.e., healthy SGN). Together with the observation that incomplete degeneration of the peripheral processes (i.e., dendritic lesion) had no significant effect on PE, we conclude that for healthy SGNs the cathodic-leading pulse elicits a spike at the somata or at the nearest Node of Ranvier at the peripheral processes.

2) Central activation with anodic-leading pulses

As the threshold for anodic-leading pulses was neither elevated by acute nor chronic soma lesions, we conclude that it elicits a spike further central to the soma, likely within the auditory nerve.

3) Changes with neural health

After acute soma lesions the latency to anodic-leading pulses was prolonged. This indicates a more peripheral activation as compared to the healthy situation. We propose that this is due to an

(temporary) opening of a current path into the lesioned tissue and stimulation at the “stumps” of the axons close to the damaged soma region (i.e., cathodic spike-initiation site). Latencies for the chronically deafened ears did not differ significantly from control ears, indicating that (as expected) the processes at the initial lesion site were no longer excitable. There was, however, a polarity-specific change when stimulating close to areas with chronically lesioned SGN somata. This elevation of cathodic thresholds implies higher current spread and thus, the spike initiation likely included a population of remaining healthy SGN in the vicinity of the lesion. We propose a combination of both central and apical/basal shifts in spike-initiation site and will perform midbrain recordings to further describe the contribution of this proposed offsite stimulation.

Please note that changes were observed at threshold level. At higher current levels, both polarities are likely activating central axons, similar to what has been reported in human modelling studies ([Heshmat et al., 2021](#); [Rattay et al., 2001a, 2001b](#)).

Funding

The project was granted by the MHH-plus foundation of the Hannover Medical School and supported by the MED-EL company (proving guinea pig adjusted CIs) and the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (Cluster of Excellence: Hearing4All, DFG Exc. 2177). Besides the financial support, the funding sources were not involved in any aspects of the study, the interpretation, nor publication of the results.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Wiebke Konerding: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Julie Arenberg:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Andrej Kral:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Peter Baumhoff:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation.

Acknowledgements

We thank Daniela Kühne for preparing the histological specimens and microscopy pictures and Karl-Jürgen Kühne for supervising the μ CT scanning procedure. We thank the anonymous reviewers for their insightful comments and valuable suggestions.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Arslan, N.O., Luo, X., 2022. Assessing the relationship between pitch perception and neural health in cochlear implant users. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 23 (6), 875–887.
- Bahmer, A., Baumann, U., 2013. Effects of electrical pulse polarity shape on intra cochlear neural responses in humans: triphasic pulses with cathodic second phase. *Hear. Res.* 306, 123–130.
- Bierer, J.A., Deeks, J.M., Billig, A.J., Carlyon, R.P., 2015. Comparison of signal and gap-detection thresholds for focused and broad cochlear implant electrode configurations. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 16, 273–284.
- Briaire, J.J., Frijns, J.H., 2005. Unraveling the electrically evoked compound action potential. *Hear. Res.* 205 (1–2), 143–156.
- Brochier, T., Guérit, F., Deeks, J.M., Garcia, C., Bance, M., Carlyon, R.P., 2021. Evaluating and comparing behavioural and electrophysiological estimates of neural health in cochlear implant users. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 22 (1), 67–80.
- Brown, D.J., Patuzzi, R.B., 2010. Evidence that the compound action potential (CAP) from the auditory nerve is a stationary potential generated across dura mater. *Hear. Res.* 267 (1–2), 12–26.
- Carlyon, R.P., Cosentino, S., Deeks, J.M., Parkinson, W., Arenberg, J.A., 2018. Effect of stimulus polarity on detection thresholds in cochlear implant users: relationships with average threshold, gap detection, and rate discrimination. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 19, 559–567.
- Carlyon, R.P., Deeks, J.M., Macherey, O., 2013. Polarity effects on place pitch and loudness for three cochlear-implant designs and at different cochlear sites. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 134 (1), 503–509.
- Carlyon, R.P., Goehring, T., 2021. Cochlear implant research and development in the twenty-first century: a critical update. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 22 (5), 481–508.
- De Groote, E., Carlyon, R.P., Deeks, J.M., Macherey, O., 2024. Effects of selective stimulation of apical electrodes on temporal pitch perception by cochlear implant recipients. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 156 (3), 2060–2076.
- Dong, Y., Briaire, J.J., Christiaan Stronks, H., Frijns, J.H.M., 2022. Short- and long-latency components of the eCAP reveal different refractory properties. *Hear. Res.* 420, 108522.
- Fellner, A., Wenger, C., Heshmat, A., Rattay, F., 2024. Auditory nerve fiber excitability for alternative electrode placement in the obstructed human cochlea: electrode insertion in scala vestibuli versus scala tympani. *J. Neural Eng.* 21 (4), 046034.
- Goehring, T., Archer-Boyd, A., Deeks, J.M., Arenberg, J.G., Carlyon, R.P., 2019. A site-selection strategy based on polarity sensitivity for cochlear implants: effects on spectro-temporal resolution and speech perception. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 20 (4), 431–448.
- Guérit, F., Marozeau, J., Epp, B., Carlyon, R.P., 2020. Effect of the relative timing between same-polarity pulses on thresholds and loudness in cochlear implant users. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 21 (6), 497–510.
- He, S., Teagle, H.F., Buchman, C.A., 2017. The electrically evoked compound action potential: from laboratory to clinic. *Front. Neurosci.* 11, 339.
- Heshmat, A., Sajedi, S., Schrott-Fischer, A., Rattay, F., 2021. Polarity sensitivity of human auditory nerve fibers based on pulse shape, cochlear implant stimulation strategy and array. *Front. Neurosci.* 15, 751599.
- Hughes, M.L., 2022. Characterizing polarity sensitivity in cochlear implant recipients: demographic effects and potential implications for estimating neural health. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 23 (2), 301–318.
- Hughes, M.L., 2023. Electrically evoked compound action potential polarity sensitivity, refractory-recovery, and behavioral multi-pulse integration as potential indices of neural health in cochlear-implant recipients. *Hear. Res.* 433, 108764.
- Hughes, M.L., Goehring, J.L., Baudhuin, J.L., 2017. Effects of stimulus polarity and artifact reduction method on the electrically evoked compound action potential. *Ear Hear.* 38 (3), 332–343.
- Iyer, J.S., Batts, S.A., Chu, K.K., Sahin, M.I., Leung, H.M., Tearney, G.J., Stankovic, K.M., 2016. Micro-optical coherence tomography of the mammalian cochlea. *Sci. Rep.* 6 (1), 33288.
- Jahn, K.N., Arenberg, J.G., 2019a. Evaluating psychophysical polarity sensitivity as an indirect estimate of neural status in cochlear implant listeners. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 20 (4), 415–430.
- Jahn, K.N., Arenberg, J.G., 2019b. Polarity sensitivity in pediatric and adult cochlear implant listeners. *Trends Hear.* 23, 2331216519862987.
- Jahn, K.N., Arenberg, J.G., 2020. Identifying cochlear implant channels with relatively poor electrode-neuron interfaces using the electrically evoked compound action potential. *Ear Hear.* 41 (4), 961–973.
- Javel, E., Shepherd, R.K., 2000. Electrical stimulation of the auditory nerve: III. Response initiation sites and temporal fine structure. *Hear. Res.* 140 (1–2), 45–76.
- Kalkman, R.K., Briaire, J.J., Dekker, D.M., Frijns, J.H., 2022. The relation between polarity sensitivity and neural degeneration in a computational model of cochlear implant stimulation. *Hear. Res.* 415, 108413.
- Keppeler, D., Kampshoff, C.A., Thirumalai, A., Duque-Afonso, C.J., Schaeper, J.J., Quilitz, T., Töpferwien, M., Vogl, C., Hessler, R., Meyer, A., 2021. Multiscale photonic imaging of the native and implanted cochlea. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 118 (18), e2014472118.
- Klop, W.M.C., Hartlooper, A., Briare, J.J., Frijns, J.H., 2004. A new method for dealing with the stimulus artefact in electrically evoked compound action potential measurements. *Acta Otolaryngol.* 124 (2), 137–143.
- Konerding, W., Arenberg, J.G., Kral, A., Baumhoff, P., 2021. Inferior colliculus recordings to assess focal spiral ganglion neuron lesions. In: Paper presented at the *MidWinter Meeting of the Association for Research in Otolaryngology (ARO)*.
- Konerding, W., Arenberg, J.G., Kral, A., Baumhoff, P., 2022. Late electrically-evoked compound action potentials as markers for acute micro-lesions of spiral ganglion neurons. *Hear. Res.* 413.
- Konerding, W., Arenberg, J., Sznabel, D., Kral, A., Baumhoff, P., 2025. An electrically evoked compound action potential marker for local spiral ganglion neuron degeneration: the failure index. *J. Neurosci.* 45 (7).
- Konerding, W., Baumhoff, P., Kral, A., 2023. Anodic polarity minimizes facial nerve stimulation as a side effect of cochlear implantation. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 24 (1), 31–46.
- Lang, H., 2016. Loss, degeneration, and preservation of the spiral ganglion neurons and their processes. In: Dabdoub, A., Fritsch, B., Popper, A., Fay, R. (Eds.), *The Primary Auditory Neurons of the Mammalian Cochlea*. Springer, pp. 229–262.
- Loeb, G.E., Byers, C.L., Rebscher, S.J., Casey, D.E., Fong, M.M., Schindler, R.A., Gray, R. F., Merzenich, M.M., 1983. Design and fabrication of an experimental cochlear prosthesis. *Med. Biol. Eng. Comput.* 21, 241–254.
- Macherey, O., Carlyon, R.P., van Wiering, A., Deeks, J.M., Wouters, J., 2008. Higher sensitivity of human auditory nerve fibers to positive electrical currents. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 9, 241–251.
- Macherey, O., Carlyon, R.P., Chatron, J., Roman, S., 2017. Effect of pulse polarity on thresholds and on non-monotonic loudness growth in cochlear implant users. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 18, 513–527.
- Macherey, O., Cazals, Y., 2016. Effects of pulse shape and polarity on sensitivity to cochlear implant stimulation: a chronic study in guinea pigs. *Adv. Exp. Med. Biol.* 894, 133–142. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-25474-6_15.
- Mesnildrey, Q., Venail, F., Carlyon, R.P., Macherey, O., 2020. Polarity sensitivity as a potential correlate of neural degeneration in cochlear implant users. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 21 (1), 89–104.
- Miller, C.A., Abbas, P.J., Rubinstein, J.T., Robinson, B.K., Matsuoka, A.J., Woodworth, G., 1998. Electrically evoked compound action potentials of guinea pig and cat: responses to monopolar, monophasic stimulation. *Hear. Res.* 119 (1), 142–154.
- Miller, C.A., Abbas, P.J., Hay-McCutcheon, M.J., Robinson, B.K., Nourski, K.V., Jeng, F., 2004. Intracochlear and extracochlear ECAPs suggest antidromic action potentials. *Hear. Res.* 198 (1–2), 75–86.
- Miller, C.A., Abbas, P.J., Robinson, B.K., Rubinstein, J.T., Matsuoka, A.J., 1999. Electrically evoked single-fiber action potentials from cat: responses to monopolar, monophasic stimulation. *Hear. Res.* 130 (1–2), 197–218.
- Miller, C.A., Robinson, B.K., Rubinstein, J.T., Abbas, P.J., Runge-Samuelson, C.L., 2001. Auditory nerve responses to monophasic and biphasic electric stimuli. *Hear. Res.* 151 (1–2), 79–94.
- Navntoft, C.A., Marozeau, J., Barkat, T.R., 2020. Ramped pulse shapes are more efficient for cochlear implant stimulation in an animal model. *Sci. Rep.* 10 (1), 3288.
- Pietsch, M., Aguirre Dávila, L., Erfurt, P., Avci, E., Lenarz, T., Kral, A., 2017. Spiral form of the human cochlea results from spatial constraints. *Sci. Rep.* 7 (1), 7500.
- Potrusil, T., Heshmat, A., Sajedi, S., Wenger, C., Chacko, L.J., Glueckert, R., Schrott-Fischer, A., Rattay, F., 2020. Finite element analysis and three-dimensional reconstruction of tonotopically aligned human auditory fiber pathways: a computational environment for modeling electrical stimulation by a cochlear implant based on micro-CT. *Hear. Res.* 393, 108001.
- Ramekers, D., Versnel, H., Strahl, S.B., Klis, S.F., Grolman, W., 2015. Recovery characteristics of the electrically stimulated auditory nerve in deafened guinea pigs: relation to neuronal status. *Hear. Res.* 321, 12–24.
- Ramekers, D., Versnel, H., Strahl, S.B., Smeets, E.M., Klis, S.F., Grolman, W., 2014. Auditory-nerve responses to varied inter-phase gap and phase duration of the electric pulse stimulus as predictors for neuronal degeneration. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 15, 187–202.
- Rattay, F., Danner, S.M., 2014. Peak I of the human auditory brainstem response results from the somatic regions of type I spiral ganglion cells: evidence from computer modeling. *Hear. Res.* 315, 67–79.
- Rattay, F., Leao, R.N., Felix, H., 2001a. A model of the electrically excited human cochlear neuron. II. Influence of the three-dimensional cochlear structure on neural excitability. *Hear. Res.* 153 (1–2), 64–79.
- Rattay, F., Lutter, P., Felix, H., 2001b. A model of the electrically excited human cochlear neuron: I. Contribution of neural substructures to the generation and propagation of spikes. *Hear. Res.* 153 (1–2), 43–63.
- Recugnat, M., 2022. *Modelling the Physiology of Spiral Ganglion Neurons*. Macquarie University.
- Skidmore, J., Ramekers, D., Bruce, I.C., He, S., 2022a. Comparison of response properties of the electrically stimulated auditory nerve reported in human listeners and in animal models. *Hear. Res.* 426, 108643.
- Skidmore, J., Ramekers, D., Coles, D.J., Schwartz-Leyzac, K.C., Pflingst, B.E., He, S., 2022b. A broadly applicable method for characterizing the slope of the electrically evoked compound action potential amplitude growth function. *Ear Hear.* 43 (1), 150–164.
- Spitzer, E.R., Choi, S., Hughes, M.L., 2019. The effect of stimulus polarity on the relation between pitch ranking and ECAP spread of excitation in cochlear implant users. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 20, 279–290.
- Sriperumbudur, K.K., Appali, R., Gummer, A.W., van Rienen, U., 2024. Understanding the impact of modiolus porosity on stimulation of spiral ganglion neurons by cochlear implants. *Sci. Rep.* 14 (1), 9593.
- Undurraga, J.A., Carlyon, R.P., Wouters, J., Van Wieringen, A., 2013. The polarity sensitivity of the electrically stimulated human auditory nerve measured at the level of the brainstem. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 14, 359–377.
- Undurraga, J.A., Van Wieringen, A., Carlyon, R.P., Macherey, O., Wouters, J., 2010. Polarity effects on neural responses of the electrically stimulated auditory nerve at different cochlear sites. *Hear. Res.* 269 (1–2), 146–161.

Van den Honert, C., Stypulkowski, P.H., 1987. Single fiber mapping of spatial excitation patterns in the electrically stimulated auditory nerve. *Hear. Res.* 29 (2-3), 195-206.

Xu, L., Skidmore, J., Luo, J., Chao, X., Wang, R., Wang, H., He, S., 2020. The effect of pulse polarity on neural response of the electrically-stimulated cochlear nerve in

children with cochlear nerve deficiency and children with normal-sized cochlear nerves. *Ear Hear.* 41 (5), 1306.

Zheng, L., Feng, Z., Xu, Y., Yuan, Y., Hu, Y., 2022. An anodic phase can facilitate rather than weaken a cathodic phase to activate neurons in biphasic-pulse axonal stimulations. *Front. Neurosci.* 16, 823423.